

Phase Transitions in Complexity: Active Cell Growth, Shannon Entropy, and Kolmogorov Complexity in Dependent Cell Ranges of Mobile Automata with Non-Local Rules

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This paper investigates phase transitions in complexity within mobile automata governed by non-local rules. Unlike traditional cellular automata, mobile automata involve a single active cell navigating and updating a one-dimensional array of binary-state cells based on a rule set. By varying the number and symmetry of dependent cells in non-local rules, we observe abrupt changes in system behavior that we identify as computational phase transitions. Using active cell growth and two complementary metrics—Shannon block entropy and an estimate of Kolmogorov complexity based on lossless compression—we quantitatively analyze the complexity of automata across a range of dependent cell configurations. Our results reveal that certain increases in non-locality trigger dramatic shifts in entropy and compressibility, while other expansions produce negligible or even simplifying effects. We categorize the observed transitions into classes based on their

entropy and growth patterns and demonstrate that complexity does not scale linearly with non-locality. This study provides a formal foundation for understanding structural complexity in mobile automata and contributes to the broader theory of emergent computation in simple rule-based systems.

Keywords: Mobile automata, non-local rules, phase transitions, Shannon Block Entropy, Kolmogorov Complexity, Active cell growth, Emergent behavior, Cellular automata

1. Introduction

Mobile automata are a subset of one-dimensional cellular automata in which a single active cell moves through a linear array of binary-state cells, updating the configuration based on a specified rule. Originally explored in depth by Stephen Wolfram in “A New Kind of Science” [1], mobile automata exemplify how simple, local mechanisms can generate surprisingly rich and complex behavior. According to Wolfram’s Principle of Computational Equivalence, even these minimal systems are capable of exhibiting computational behaviors comparable to those of universal Turing machines [2].

The broader study of cellular automata has long provided a foundation for exploring emergent computation. Cook’s landmark 2004 proof of the universality of Rule 110 [3] confirmed that deterministic, rule-based systems can simulate any algorithmic process. Mitchell, Crutchfield, and Hraber [4] demonstrated how cellular automata serve as idealized laboratories for investigating self-organization and complexity in both biological and physical systems. These systems have been shown to evolve through a wide spectrum of behaviors—from fixed points to periodicity to chaos—depending on the structure of their update rules.

While most prior research has focused on local interactions, this paper turns to a less-explored but highly consequential domain: non-local rules in mobile automata. In these systems, the active cell is allowed to base its update on cells at arbitrary distances, expanding the computational landscape. Non-locality has been previously examined in contexts such as Li’s work on non-local cellular automata [5], where long-range interactions were shown to dramatically affect emergent patterns. Similarly, the role of non-locality in complex systems has been

studied more generally in the context of global dependency and distributed behavior [6].

In this paper, we explore the emergence of phase transitions in complexity as the dependent cell range is varied in mobile automata with non-local rules. By employing Shannon block entropy and Kolmogorov complexity estimates as quantitative metrics, we analyze how increasing the number, range, and symmetry of dependent cells alters the automaton's behavior. This builds upon earlier studies in self-organized criticality and complexity measures [7], while connecting to computational modeling traditions in domains like systems biology and fluid mechanics [8].

By formalizing and classifying phase transitions in this space, we aim to contribute a novel framework for understanding how computational complexity arises and shifts in mobile automata. Computational details are available in [9].

2. Construction of Non-Local Rules

In traditional mobile automata, the state of an active cell at time t is determined by its own state and the states of its immediate neighbors (dependent cells) at time $t - 1$. Non-local rules introduce an extended range of interaction, where the active cell can be influenced by cells located several steps away by increasing the range of dependent cells.

For example, consider an automaton where the active cell at position n is influenced by cells at positions $n - 4, n - 2, n + 2, n + 4$. This type of rule defines a broader neighborhood for decision-making, allowing more complex dynamics to emerge.

Mathematically, non-local rules can be formalized as a tuple:

$$\text{Rule} = \{s, d, \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k\}\} \quad (1)$$

where:

- s is the state of the active cell,
- d determines the direction in which the active cell moves, and
- p_i are the positions relative to the active cell that influence its next state.

The rule set is constructed as follows:

- The state s of the active cell is updated based on the states of cells located at p_i , which may be positive or negative offsets from the active cell.
- The movement d of the active cell is determined by the result of the rule application, which depends on the configuration of cells at these non-local positions.

▲ **Figure 1.** A non-local rule plot showing a mobile automaton with dependent cells 4 cells to the left, 2 cells to the left, the active cell itself, and 2 cells to the right (relative to the active cell). In this case, the state of the active cell stays as black while it moves 1 cell to the right for the next timestep.

The non-local mobile automaton model exhibits intriguing behaviors as we vary the range of dependent cells. By adjusting the range of non-local interactions, the automaton's dynamics become more complex, often generating patterns that extend across a larger spatial domain. These behaviors highlight the significance of the range parameter in influencing how the automaton evolves over time. In some contexts, the system's oscillations tend to grow, and the spatial patterns formed by the active cells change, reflecting the underlying influence of non-local dependencies on cellular interactions.

▲ **Figure 2.** The behavior of a mobile automaton with the same initial conditions using different dependent cell ranges. As the range gets increased with consistent rules, the oscillation of the active cell gets into larger and larger intervals.

3. Complexity Measures for Phase Transitions

3.1 Active Cell Growth

Active cell growth in mobile automata represents the number of cells that transition from an inactive (white) state to an active (black) state over time. In our study of mobile automata with non-local rules, we focus on how the number of active cells increases as the automaton evolves. This is particularly relevant when analyzing automata with multiple active cells, where the growth rate of active cells can highlight the impact of non-local dependencies on the automaton's complexity.

▲ **Figure 3.** A non-local mobile automaton with multiple active cells that shows considerable complexity. Its dependent cells are 3 cells to the left of the active cell, the active cell itself, and 2 cells to the right of the active cell.

When there is only one active cell, the growth of active cells tends to be more predictable, depending on the range and configuration of the non-local rule set. However, when multiple active cells are introduced, the behavior becomes more complex and less deterministic, with new patterns emerging from the interactions between the cells.

To plot and determine the number of active cells at each step, we can scan each step of the automaton for any cells that contain the black dot (which indicates an active cell).

▲ **Figure 4.** The active cell chart for the mobile automata in Figure 3. The seemingly random distribution of active cells in the mobile automaton plot is visually quantifiable in the seemingly random dips and peaks of the graph.

To continue the discussion on active cell growth, an essential element of complexity in mobile automata is the pattern created by the interaction between active and dependent cells. These patterns usually become more intricate as the number of dependent cells increases or the range of interaction between them broadens. This complexity manifests visually in a widening array of active cells as rules evolve, giving rise to more dynamic behavior over time.

By incrementally adjusting the parameters for non-local rules, we can observe the impact on the automaton's evolution. The visualizations shown below depict the automaton's behavior under different dependent cell ranges, providing insights into the critical point (known as the threshold of complexity) where simple behavior gives way to complex, non-linear patterns.

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▲ **Figure 5.** The evolution of a non-local mobile automaton with multiple active cells for different dependent cell ranges. The behavior suddenly switches from simple and repetitive to complex and dynamic at the point when the dependent cell range is $\{-2, 0, 3\}$, indicating a threshold of complexity at that point.

Through plotting the active cell charts for all of the mobile automata,

we can visualize the threshold for complexity in a graphical format.

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▲ **Figure 6.** The active cell chart for Figure 5. We can see the threshold of complexity as the regular lines changing into seemingly random peaks and dips as soon as the dependent cell range gets past a certain point.

As we examine the behavior of mobile automata with non-local rules, distinct patterns emerge depending on the configuration of dependent cell ranges. In some cases, when the dependent cells are symmetric relative to the active cell, such as in ranges like $\{-2, 0, 2\}$, we often observe complex, non-repetitive behavior. The symmetry leads to a chaotic growth pattern where the automaton explores a variety of configurations without settling into a repeating cycle. This complexity is a key feature of mobile automata when the rule structure remains balanced on both sides of the active cell.

In contrast, when the dependent cell ranges are asymmetric, for instance, $\{-2, 0, 3\}$, the automaton tends to exhibit a simpler, repetitive behavior. Here, the lack of symmetry reduces the complexity of interactions between cells, often leading to regular and predictable patterns. The shift from chaotic to ordered behavior is significant in understanding how the placement and selection of dependent cells drive the overall system's behavior.

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▲ **Figure 7.** A specific initial condition for a mobile automaton where symmetric dependent cell ranges ($\{-2, 0, 2\}$) lead to complex behavior, while asymmetric ranges ($\{-2, 0, 3\}$) result in simpler, repetitive patterns.

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▲ **Figure 8.** The active cell graph for Figure 7. The automata with asymmetric dependent cell ranges show very periodic and predictable behavior in terms of active cell growth, while the symmetric dependent cell ranges exhibit more complex, seemingly random behavior with active cell growth

However, as shown in Figure 9, increasing the dependent cell range does not necessarily lead to more complex behavior. In fact, small adjustments to the range—such as increasing it by a single step on one side—can entirely simplify the behavior, resulting in simple, linear growth rather than chaotic expansion. This counterintuitive result highlights the sensitivity of mobile automata to minor changes in their rule structures, where increasing the range by even one unit leads to complete behavioral simplification.

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▲ **Figure 9.** An example in which increasing the dependent cell range does not always increase complexity. In these examples, extending the range by just one unit simplifies the initially complex behavior of the automaton.

While one might intuitively expect that increasing the dependent cell range introduces greater complexity, Figure 9 demonstrates a case where

the opposite occurs. The initial configuration with a small, local rule set $(-1, 0, 1)$ generates dynamic and seemingly chaotic behavior, whereas even a slight increase in the dependent cell range results in a rapid suppression of complexity. This trend is further quantified in Figure 10, where the active cell chart shows that only the $(-1, 0, 1)$ case maintains any degree of variability, while all larger dependent cell ranges exhibit a trivial and nearly constant number of active cells. This suggests that non-locality can, in some cases, enforce strict determinism and limit the unpredictability of the automaton's evolution.

▲ **Figure 10.** The active cell chart for Figure 9. Only the first dependent cell range, which uses only local rules, shows any kind of complexity with active cell growth. However, increasing the dependent cell range immediately simplifies and reduces the chaos of the active cell growth.

So far, we have looked at non-local mobile automata with 3 dependent cells, but non-local rules can expand to any n number of dependent cells, governed by 2^n configuration rules. Figure 11 presents a mobile automaton with a larger dependent cell range of $(-3, -1, 0, 2)$ and a visualization of all 2^4 possible rules governing its behavior. This rule space provides insight into how different update functions interact with expanded non-local dependencies.

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▲ **Figure 11.** The mobile automaton evolution for a rule with four dependent cells $(-3, -1, 0, 2)$, alongside a visualization of all possible 2^4 update rules. The rule plot provides a comprehensive view of the automaton's decision space, revealing patterns that emerge as dependency structures become more distributed.

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▲ **Figure 12.** The active cell chart for the mobile automaton in Figure 11, with four dependent cells $(-3, -1, 0, 2)$. Unlike automata with simpler dependent cell ranges, this configuration exhibits more fluctuating growth in the number of active cells, suggesting a phase transition towards more complex behavior.

The active cell charts, as a metric of complexity, illustrate a clear distinction between complex and simple behaviors based on the structure of dependent cell ranges. Local rules, such as $(-1, 0, 1)$, generate irregular, fluctuating growth in the number of active cells, while increasing the range of dependencies often leads to stabilization and periodicity, or even complete suppression of activity. However, while active cell growth provides insight into macroscopic trends, it does not fully capture the underlying information content of the system.

To further quantify the complexity of mobile automata with non-local rules, we turn to Shannon block entropy, which measures the unpredictability and diversity of local configurations within the automaton's evolution. Unlike active cell growth, which tracks only the number of active sites, Shannon entropy allows us to assess the richness of patterns within the automaton's state space. In the next section, we examine how entropy changes as a function of the dependent cell range and investigate whether it aligns with the complexity thresholds observed in the active cell analysis.

3.2 Shannon Block Entropy

While the previous section analyzed complexity through the growth of active cells, this alone does not fully capture the information-theoretic complexity of the system. A system with a high number of active cells could still exhibit highly regular behavior, whereas a system with few active cells could generate intricate, unpredictable patterns. To provide a more detailed quantification of complexity, we analyze Shannon block entropy, a metric that measures the diversity and unpredictability of local configurations within the automaton's evolution.

Shannon entropy for block structures of length m is computed as:

$$S_m = -\sum_i P(i) \log_2 P(i) \quad (2)$$

where $P(i)$ represents the probability of encountering a specific block of size m in the automaton's evolution [10]. By varying m , we can examine how the automaton's complexity scales across different pattern lengths.

We apply this measure to mobile automata with different dependent cell ranges to investigate whether the previously observed thresholds of complexity in active cell growth correspond to structural complexity within the automaton's configuration space. The following results demonstrate how Shannon block entropy evolves as the dependent cell range increases.

Figure 11 presents the Shannon entropy values for increasing dependent cell ranges for the rule in Figure 5. This analysis helps determine whether increasing non-locality consistently leads to greater complexity or whether certain transitions in dependent cell ranges mark a threshold between simple and complex behavior. Here, the threshold of complexity is more clear, as the Shannon block entropy suddenly jumps when the dependent cell range hits $(-2, 0, 3)$.

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▲ **Figure 13.** Shannon block entropy for the mobile automaton shown in Figure 5 with varying dependent cell ranges. The x-axis represents the degree of non-locality (the range of dependent cells), while the y-axis represents Shannon block entropy. After the sudden jump in complexity, the entropy of the mobile automaton levels off and stabilizes.

The previous figure established how Shannon block entropy evolves as the degree of non-locality increases. We observed distinct shifts in entropy, suggesting possible phase transitions where complexity either rises sharply or stabilizes. However, one rule alone does not fully capture the structural differences in automaton behavior. In the figure below, which depicts the Shannon entropy for the rule in Figure 7, the figure shows a different picture that matches up with our observations on the active cell charts. Mainly, in some rules, the complexity of a mobile automaton depends on whether the dependent cell range is symmetric or asymmetric.

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▲ **Figure 14.** Shannon block entropy for the mobile automaton shown in Figure 7 with varying dependent cell ranges. The entropy alternates between complexity stages as the dependent cell ranges switch between symmetric and asymmetric.

The oscillatory pattern in Figure 12 illustrates how the alternation between symmetric and asymmetric dependent cell ranges leads to distinct shifts in Shannon entropy. This suggests that symmetry plays a fundamental role in determining whether a mobile automaton exhibits structured complexity or repetitive behavior. To further investigate this phenomenon, Figure 13 presents another rule configuration where increasing the degree of non-locality results in a rapid collapse of entropy. Unlike the previous case, where complexity alternated in a structured way, this rule demonstrates an immediate transition to minimal entropy, highlighting that certain rule structures inherently resist complexity growth beyond a specific threshold. This contrast reinforces the idea that different mobile automata exhibit qualitatively different phase transitions, depending on how their rules interact with increasing non-locality.

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▲ **Figure 15.** Shannon block entropy for the mobile automaton shown in Figure 9 with varying dependent cell ranges. The entropy immediately plunges as soon as the dependent cell range is non-local (i.e. $> (-1, 0, 1)$).

To contrast the behavior in Figure 13, Figure 14 presents a case where the entropy remains virtually unchanged regardless of the degree of non-locality. This highlights a different kind of phase transition—one where increasing the dependent cell range has no significant effect on the system’s complexity. The automaton’s behavior is invariant under changes in non-locality, implying that certain rules are inherently resistant to shifts in complexity.

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▲ **Figure 16.** Shannon block entropy for a mobile automaton with varying dependent cell ranges. The dependent cell range does not significantly affect the automaton’s entropy.

The analysis now shifts from examining the Shannon entropy of mobile automata with three dependent cells (Figure 13, 14, 15, 16) to those with four dependent cells (Figure 17). In the case of three-dependent-cell automata, entropy remains largely unchanged across different dependent cell ranges, indicating a stable complexity level. However, for four-dependent-cell automata, we observe a more dynamic entropy distribution. Notably, the entropy values for certain configurations with four dependent cells are not necessarily higher than those for three-dependent-cell automata. This suggests that increasing the number of dependent cells does not always correlate with increased complexity—rather, the structure introduced by additional dependencies can sometimes reduce entropy by enforcing more rigid, less chaotic behavior.

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▲ **Figure 17.** Shannon block entropy for the mobile automata shown in Figure 11 with varying dependent cell ranges. The entropy does not exhibit a strictly increasing trend as the number of dependent cells increases, highlighting that the addition of more dependent cells does not necessarily lead to greater complexity.

While Shannon block entropy provides insights into the statistical complexity of mobile automata by measuring the diversity of state transitions over time, it does not fully capture the underlying algorithmic complexity of the system. Specifically, Shannon entropy is limited to quantifying unpredictability based on probability distributions, whereas a metric like Kolmogorov complexity offers a different perspective by assessing the minimal description length required to encode the automaton’s evolution. To further formalize our observations, we now transition to analyzing the Kolmogorov complexity of these mobile automata. This will allow us to compare how well Shannon entropy aligns with a measure that considers the computational irreducibility of the automaton’s behavior, helping to identify deeper structural phase transitions.

3.3 Kolmogorov Complexity

While Shannon entropy quantifies the expected information content of a source based on the statistical distribution of its symbols, Kolmogorov complexity offers a fundamentally different lens through

which to evaluate complexity—one that is algorithmic rather than probabilistic. The Kolmogorov complexity $K(x)$ of a finite string x is defined as the length of the shortest program that outputs x on a fixed universal Turing machine. In essence, it measures the minimal description length required to fully reproduce a string, and thus reflects the string’s degree of compressibility or structure [11].

Unlike Shannon entropy, Kolmogorov complexity is incomputable; there exists no general algorithm capable of determining $K(x)$ for arbitrary strings. This incomputability arises from its relationship with the Halting Problem and the unbounded nature of general program search. Nevertheless, it can be approximated using lossless compression algorithms where the size of the compressed string serves as an upper bound [12]:

$$K(x) \approx |C(x)| \quad (3)$$

Here, $C(x)$ denotes a lossless compression of x (e.g., via LZ77 or DEFLATE), and $|C(x)|$ is its length. The shorter the compressed representation, the lower the estimated complexity. In this work, we adopt this compression-based approach to estimate Kolmogorov complexity using the function `KolmogorovComplexityEstimate`, which applies practical compression heuristics to the evolution output of mobile automata.

In[]:=*

```
binaryString [automatonEvolution_] :=  
StringJoin [ToString /@ automatonEvolution];
```

In[]:=*

```
KolmogorovComplexityEstimate [  
automatonEvolution_] := ByteCount [  
Compress [binaryString [automatonEvolution]]]
```

As noted in Lindgren and Nordahl’s foundational work, *Complexity Measures and Cellular Automata* (1988), Kolmogorov complexity is closely related to Shannon entropy in that both converge for long sequences generated by stationary stochastic processes [13]. Specifically, they observe that:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{K(x_1^n)}{n} = H \quad (4)$$

for almost all sequences x_1^n generated by a source with entropy rate H . This convergence underscores the alignment between algorithmic and probabilistic notions of complexity, particularly for long outputs.

In the context of mobile automata, we find that estimated Kolmogorov complexity follows a trajectory similar to that of Shannon block entropy. Both metrics capture changes in structural regularity and emergent behavior as we vary the dependent cell range of the automaton. In Figure 18, we present a consolidated view of the Kolmogorov complexity results, which closely parallel the established entropy trends.

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▲ **Figure 18.** Kolmogorov complexity over increasing dependent cell ranges for each of the mobile automaton rules discussed in Sections 3.1 and 3.2.

In Figure 18, with each plot corresponding to a different rule, the overall patterns closely mirror those observed in the Shannon block

entropy plots for the same rule—highlighting similar phase transitions, complexity jumps, and saturation behavior. These estimates, derived from lossless compression, reinforce the consistency between algorithmic and statistical complexity measures in capturing structural change.

However, when comparing the Shannon block entropy and Kolmogorov complexity plot for the mobile automaton with 4 dependent cells, a noticeable divergence emerges between the two complexity metrics. In prior examples, both entropy and complexity tended to rise and fall together, often exhibiting the same abrupt transitions at particular dependent cell ranges. However, for this 4-cell rule, that pattern breaks down. For instance, while the Shannon entropy graph shows a sharp dip at the dependent range $\{-3, -2, 0, 5\}$, indicating reduced unpredictability, the Kolmogorov complexity at that same point remains relatively high. This discrepancy suggests that although entropy is capturing the unpredictability in local configurations, the broader compressibility of the space-time pattern—the aspect captured by Kolmogorov complexity—might be shaped by different structural features not evident in local entropy alone. This divergence between Shannon entropy and Kolmogorov complexity estimates also aligns with findings from Zenil’s work, who emphasized that while entropy captures statistical regularity, compression-based Kolmogorov estimates capture deeper structural algorithmic randomness [12].

4. Identifying & Analyzing Phase Transitions

A central goal of this paper is to uncover how the complexity of mobile automata changes as we increase the degree of non-locality, i.e., as we expand the range of dependent cells in the update rules. In this section, we formalize the concept of phase transitions in mobile automata and systematically analyze them using both Shannon block entropy and Kolmogorov complexity metrics across multiple automaton rules.

4.1 Defining Phase Transitions in Mobile Automata

In statistical physics, a phase transition refers to an abrupt change in the macroscopic behavior of a system due to a small change in a control parameter. Analogously, we define a computational phase transition in mobile automata as a sudden or qualitative shift in the complexity of the

automaton's evolution caused by a small change in the dependent cell range.

Let $R = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n\}$ be a sequence of dependent cell ranges ordered by increasing non-locality, and let $C(r_i)$ represent a chosen complexity metric (e.g., Shannon block entropy or Kolmogorov complexity) evaluated for an automaton with range r_i . A phase transition is identified by a non-smooth jump in $C(r)$, such as a sharp increase or drop that is not explained by noise or local fluctuations.

4.2 Evidence of Phase Transitions Across Automata Rules

Figures 13–18 illustrate complexity measures for five distinct mobile automaton rules across sequences of dependent cell ranges. The metrics offer strong empirical evidence of phase transitions in the behavior of these automata.

In Figure 13 and Figure 18 (top-left), we observe a clear phase transition occurring between the dependent cell ranges $\{-2, 0, 2\}$ and $\{-2, 0, 3\}$. Both the Shannon block entropy and the Kolmogorov complexity jump significantly, marking a transition from relatively low to high complexity. After this jump, the entropy and complexity stabilize, forming a plateau—indicative of a new computational phase. This stabilization implies that increasing the non-locality further does not meaningfully change the qualitative behavior of the automaton. This transition mirrors a common pattern in computational systems: a simple behavior regime (low entropy and low complexity), a rapid transition region (the “edge of chaos” or “threshold of complexity”), and a complex regime that saturates at a high entropy ceiling. We can also see this concept in the active cell growth chart in Figure 6.

Figure 14 and Figure 18 (top-right) reveal a periodic alternation in entropy as the dependent cell range toggles between symmetric and asymmetric structures. This behavior is a cyclic phase shift, where complexity does not increase or decrease monotonically with non-locality but rather depends on the spatial symmetry of the rule. For example, ranges like $\{-2, 0, 2\}$ yield higher entropy than asymmetric ones like $\{-2, 0, 3\}$, suggesting that symmetry acts as a structural parameter influencing complexity phases. Interestingly, the Kolmogorov complexity (Figure 18) for this rule mimics the entropy's jagged profile, further validating the presence of alternating computational phases,

though with some variation in the amplitude of changes.

In Figure 15 and Figure 18 (middle-left), we find a striking inverse phase transition. The automaton starts with high entropy and complexity at the local rule $\{-1, 0, 1\}$, but as soon as even minor non-locality is introduced (e.g., $\{-1, 0, 2\}$), the entropy plummets and remains low across all more extended ranges. This suggests that for certain rules, adding non-local information does not enrich the behavior but rather simplifies it, possibly by overpowering local dynamics with globally stabilizing influences.

Figure 16 and Figure 18 (middle-right) show an automaton whose entropy and Kolmogorov complexity are invariant across increasing dependent cell ranges. There are no phase transitions here; the automaton operates in a single phase regardless of locality. This result is crucial, as it demonstrates that not all automata respond to non-locality in the same way—some are structurally robust, with complexity unaffected by range modifications.

In Figure 17 and Figure 18 (bottom-left), we study a four-dependent-cell automaton, and find non-monotonic behavior in both entropy and complexity. Notably, the entropy does not exceed that of some automata with only three dependent cells (see Figure 13), suggesting that more dependency does not always yield more complexity. Here, phase transitions appear intermittently, and the relationship between rule structure and phase change is more nuanced. This provides a broader perspective: transitions depend not only on range size but also on the specific configuration of dependency.

4.3 Classes of Phase Transition Behavior

Based on these findings, I propose a tentative classification of phase transition types in mobile automata with non-local rules:

- **Type I: Complexity-Saturating Transitions**

A sudden increase in complexity followed by a plateau (e.g., Figure 13).

- **Type II: Oscillating Transitions**

Complexity alternates due to symmetric vs. asymmetric range structure (e.g., Figure 14).

- **Type III: Complexity-Suppressing Transitions**
An abrupt drop in complexity as non-locality increases (e.g., Figure 15).
- **Type IV: Invariant Behavior**
Complexity remains constant across all dependent cell ranges (e.g., Figure 16).
- **Type V: Non-Monotonic Multi-Phase Dynamics**
Complexity fluctuates in an irregular pattern across ranges (e.g., Figure 17).

These five transition types offer a new vocabulary for discussing and analyzing mobile automata with non-local rules. More generally, they reveal that non-locality is not a unidimensional control knob—it can yield a variety of effects depending on how it is introduced.

5. Conclusion

This study has revealed that mobile automata with non-local rules exhibit a rich spectrum of computational behavior as the dependent cell range increases. By analyzing both Shannon block entropy and Kolmogorov complexity across multiple rule configurations, we identified several distinct classes of computational phase transitions, where small changes in the rule’s structure—especially in the arrangement and symmetry of dependent cells—led to large, qualitative shifts in complexity.

Crucially, our findings show that complexity does not necessarily increase with the size or non-locality of the rule. In some cases, extending the dependent cell range simplified the automaton’s behavior, while in others, complexity alternated or plateaued. These results highlight the sensitive dependence of complexity on the structure and symmetry of non-local rules, challenging the assumption that more information necessarily results in more complex behavior.

For computational details, the interested reader is referred to [9]. By formalizing phase transitions in this context and classifying them into distinct behavioral regimes, this paper contributes a new framework for understanding complexity in mobile automata. While the present study focuses on one-dimensional mobile automata for simplicity, the approach can be generalized to higher-dimensional systems. We anticipate that

similar behaviors—such as the classifications of phase transitions—will persist in higher dimensions, providing a solid foundation for future investigations. Future work may build on this foundation by incorporating additional complexity measures, exploring different initial conditions, or expanding to higher-dimensional rule spaces. Nonetheless, the experimental evidence presented here strongly suggests that the space of non-local mobile automata is shaped by critical transition points—structural thresholds where complexity emerges, collapses, or stabilizes in unexpected ways.

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